

VICTORIAN

WATERCOLOUR ARTISTS

INDEX

- 5 Curatorial Statement
- 9 Charles A. Boot (1855-1930)
- 11 James Burrell Smith (1822-1897)
- 14 Edward Hastings (1781-1861)
- 16 James Holmes (1777-1860)
- 18 James Arthur Henry Jameson (1883-1923)
- 22 Reginald Jones, R.B.A. (1857–1920)
- 24 James Pollard (1792-1867)
- 26 George James Rowe (1804-1883)

CURATORIAL STATEMENT

LATE VICTORIAN AND GEORGIAN WATERCOLOURS

The 19th century is an extremely interesting period in English history, it was a time of huge transformation coupled with military might. The industrial growth and power of colonial England saw its' economic benefits credited with an extensive and varied production of art.

The vast majority of artists of this period did not take their inspiration from the industrial advancements in the same way as J.M.W. Turner did. On the contrary, they looked to a more conservative side, a mix between neo-classical and light touches of romanticism. Undoubtedly one of the benefits of the industrial age was the improvement in the quality of paper and watercolours, as well as an increased demand for drawings by the great masters and, together with the rise of the middle class, the demand for lithography and engravings increased as well.

This was the spark that ignited the formation of watercolour societies throughout 19th century England. These associations had been responsible for making watercolour an important and relevant sector in the English arts since the 18th century. Exhibitions from 1760 to 1783 positioned watercolour as an art discipline in its' own right, leaving behind the idea that it was just a sketch or a drawing tool.

These associations lasted until the end of the 18th century and laid the foundations for the creation of the Royal Academy of Arts, which in turn, from its' founding in 1768 and through the periods of George III and George IV, established English taste. However, watercolour did not reach a rank of relevance at the Royal Academy of Arts until 1943 when a watercolourist was appointed as Director of the Academy.

In response, the Society of Painters in Watercolours was founded in 1804 and soon after the Associated Artists in Watercolours (1808-1812), both established with the desire to improve the vision of watercolour, even-

tually, and after some name changes, the Royal Watercolour Society was established in 1905. However, many artists had a different perception of watercolour which led to the creation of the New Society of Painters in Water-Colours and led to its counterpart being known as the Old Water-Colour Society. However, the rivalry between them was extinguished when the Royal Academy of Arts forced the adoption of strict measures so that such exclusivity was no longer considered relevant.

The dispute between the watercolour societies brought with it experiments and the revival of old customs embodied in rivalries that led to aesthetic transformations such as the recovery of the Pre-Raphaelite palette, as well as characteristics of the work of Claude Lorraine—which generated a flow of work of tremendous beauty, we can see dark close-ups, tiny characters, winding rivers, hills, cloudy horizons, Scandinavian or German skies, landscapes full of mystery and nostalgia.

We must acknowledge that all these steps were necessary to arrive at the work of the Victorian watercolourists. The work of William Turner would have been impossible without “the battles” between associations of watercolourists, without that rivalry.

The peace that came with the Treaty of Amiens of 1802 between the United Kingdom and France prompted more than 6 000 British tourists to travel to continental Europe to see and appreciate city landscapes and customs or to admire the Louvre Museum. A phenomenon that was repeated after the Battle of Waterloo and the French defeat in 1815. These events led to a growth in the English publishing industry and with it the need for watercolours, drawings and engravings made *in situ*, to illustrate these books.

The Victorian period is the culmination of artistic skill in the use of watercolour. We can appreciate an extensive mastery in the application and use of watercolour, not only in technique but also in thematic and stylistic diversity. For some painters, watercolour represented nothing more than a *kitsch* vision of the time. But that opinion nullifies the greatness obtained in the handling and perfection of the technique.

For the time, the importance of watercolour lay in the dissemination of the arts throughout the English cities. The emergence of small associations of watercolourists around England led to the flourishing of watercolour and its practice both *amateur* and professional. That spawned a series of actions, among them the creation of art galleries which presented exhibitions outside the control of the Royal Academy of Arts and the New and Old Water-Colour Societies; they created a variety of jobs outside academia. It was a great boost and the whole community was involved with the possibilities that watercolour provided.

The impetus given to watercolour resulted in the watercolour sketch style as a way to appreciate simple lines, without finishes. The popular relationship that existed between the idea of a perfect finish and academia dissipated with the practice of sketching, which was considered as a more faithful, spontaneous and lyrical expression of reality. Realistic shapes and the qualities of the materials were exploited, permitting pieces in which a certain roughness was allowed and indeed valued. Charcoal or graphite details, brush strokes, watermarks, dry brush textures, and even direct colour blends, appeared on the paper.

The sketch became the romantic work par excellence, the desire to capture natural phenomena first-hand, an activity that marked the nineteenth century, that was more explicit and less close to the idealistic conventions of the eighteenth century. This situation forced the academies to generate winter exhibitions of watercolour sketches, beginning in 1843. The examples were somewhat disappointing since the artists presented sketches with clarity and finishes that bore little relationship to the fluidity of authentic watercolour artists and their sketched work.

The Victorian era was the high point for watercolour, watercolourists managed to get their works considered on the same level as oil painting, even the dimensions of the works increased to several feet per side. That represented another advance in the British art system, which was the manufacture of special papers for artists. The grain of the paper was modified and

significantly larger dimensions were generated. However, these were not the biggest technical advances. The creation of Indian White in 1834 is the most relevant advance in Victorian watercolour painting. Zinc Oxide, also known as White Zinc, is a white pigment used by the Romans and obtained during the smelting of copper. Victorian watercolourists used it as a primary layer to create a glossy film; with this, the wash technique emerged, attributed to J.M.W. Turner. It was also used to dull translucent watercolours, creating *gouache* or body-colour. However, market speculation and growing art criticism caused the fever in the watercolour market to die down in 1890; the inclusion and influence of French academies started the collapse of trust in watercolour as an investment. Today the numbers tell us another story.

Revisiting the artists we present has been an extraordinary job. Recovering the history of artists forgotten by critics or by history is an exciting endeavour, to say the least. Searching for the pieces amongst hundreds of images, paintings, warehouses and shops has been a rewarding job. Understanding the relevance of these artists in the history of British art is a unique opportunity to increase a private collection or simply appreciate the skills of these wonderful watercolourists without forgetting that we are the owners of an important piece of art history, that was believed to be forgotten.

Dr. Pablo Angel Lugo

March, 2021

CHARLES A. BOOT (1855-1930)

This is the perfect moment to start to talk about Charles A. Boot, a British 19th Century artist who has been hidden from the markets. The beauty of his poetic landscapes, is testament to his great mastery of the art of watercolours and the reason why his work has been eagerly sought by experts and collectors. Almost none of his output has ever been offered at auction, the first being “Figures in a Wooded Glade” presented by Case Antiques in 2020.

Unknown (Waterfall)

1881 *ca.*

270 x 195 mm

Watercolour on paper, 200 g/m²

Unknown (Bridge)

1880 *ca.*

270 x 195 mm

Watercolour on paper, 200 g/m²

JAMES BURRELL SMITH (1822-1897)

James Burrell Smith was one of the most well-known and widely exhibited 19th century English watercolour artists. He was a landscape painter and watercolourist, born in 1822. He lived mainly at Alnwick, Northumberland, England where he received tuition from Thomas Miles Richardson Senior; he later became a Drawing Master. He was known as 'Waterfall Smith' and exhibited regularly at the Royal Society of British Artists. He painted landscape views in many parts of England, in particular the Lake District, but also views of Wales and Scottish lochs and castles, but he was most fond of painting streams and waterfalls.

When talking with collectors about waterfalls and water scenes, the first name listed for this subject is James Burrell Smith. He, through his consistency in painting this subject, can rightly claim the crown. Beautiful in observation none can doubt his abilities in painting one of nature's most stunning elements

Smith travelled widely on the Continent producing river views such as Cologne on the Rhine (1865) and also scenes of Lake Como and Lake Geneva.

James Burrell Smith died on 16 December 1897 in West Kensington, London.

Examples of his work hang or have been presented in six British National Trust properties as well as the following collections and galleries: the Alnwick Castle Collection, The Wallington Gallery, Southampton City Art Gallery, the Mississippi Museum of Art, the Gaer Art Gallery, The Lytham St. Annes Art Collection, the Victoria and Albert Museum, London, the Fitzwilliam Museum, Cambridge, the Laing Art Gallery, Newcastle and the National Gallery of Wales, Cardiff. He exhibited regularly at Suffolk Street from 1850 to 1881.

Berwickshire Heath

1859

123 x 360 mm

Watercolour on paper, 240 g/m²

EDWARD HASTINGS (1781-1861)

Edward Hastings was originally from Alnwick in Northumberland and he was a portrait painter of some reputation. From 1812 he lived in Bedford Square in London. He died in Durham. There is little known of the personal history of Edward Hastings; the oldest auction sale recorded is a watercolor drawing sold in 2000 at Christie's. The most recent being a watercolor drawing sold in 2021. His specialism was watercolor drawings and paintings. The artist's quotes and indices establish that most of his pieces have been sold to private collections and museums, mostly in the United Kingdom, France, Canada and the United States.

Hastings works are displayed in the Durham County Council collection, the Art Collection of Durham University, The Sunderland Museum and The West Park Museum.

Three Children

1825

218 x 170 mm

Watercolour on paper, 240 g/m²

JAMES HOLMES (1777-1860)

James Holmes was a painter in oil and watercolour of genre scenes and miniatures. At an early age he was apprenticed to the well-known engraver, Robert Mitchell Meadows. He began attending the Royal Academy school in 1796 and first exhibited at the Royal Academy in 1798. From 1798 until 1849 Holmes exhibited 21 paintings at the Royal Academy. He became a watercolourist and in 1813 became a member of the Society of Painters in Water Colours, exhibiting two of his paintings. In 1824 he became a founding member of the Society of British Artists and a frequent exhibitor until 1850.

Holmes's portraiture of George IV led to a personal friendship; they played music together as Holmes was also a talented flautist.

Today Holmes's works can be seen the National Portrait Gallery and the Victoria and Albert Museum, both in London.

Fisher Girls by the Sea

1825

260 x 360 mm

Watercolour on paper, 200 g/m²

JAMES ARTHUR HENRY JAMESON (1883-1923)

James Arthur Henry Jameson was born in Donnybrook Co. Dublin in Ireland and educated at Eton College and Jesus College Cambridge.

Lake Connemara I

1914 *ca.*

204 x 155 mm

Watercolour on paper, 200 g/m²

Lake Connemara II

1914 *ca.*

204 x 155 mm

Watercolour on paper, 200 g/g/m²

Lake Connemara III

1914 *ca.*

204 x 155 mm

Watercolour on paper, 200 g/m²

Lake Connemara IV
1914 *ca.*
204 x 155 mm
Watercolour on paper, 200 g/m²

REGINALD JONES, R.B.A. (1857–1920)

Reginald Jones was an English landscape painter, who predominantly worked in oil, watercolour and pastel,

He lived in Eltham, Kent and also in London. He travelled widely, particularly in France, Spain and Italy producing many paintings of the landscapes he witnessed. Jones often travelled and worked with artist friends and contemporaries including Terrick Williams and Fred Kahl.

After viewing Jones' work at the Royal Institute exhibition of March 1889, the English artist and critic Walter Sickert commented 'I am not sorry for Reginald Jones or Raven Hill. Their accomplished chic can hold it's own anywhere. It is not progressive art, though a course of it might be a wholesome tonic to our stippling brigade.'

During the winter months when opportunities to travel abroad were scarce, Jones gave lessons in water-colour painting at his studio near Hyde Park, London.

Jones was elected a member of the Royal Society of British Artists in 1915. He exhibited extensively at the principal London galleries from 1880 until his death in 1920.

SOLO EXHIBITIONS

- "Britain and Brittany: Water-colour Drawings". Continental Gallery, London, 1898.
- "Central France, Northern Italy, & South of England: Water-colour Drawings". Continental Gallery, London, 1899.
- "Summer Sun & Autumn Haze (French & English Landscapes): Water-colour Drawings". Continental Gallery, London, 1901.
- "Busy Towns & Silent Nature: Water-colour Drawings". Continental Gallery, London, 1902.
- "Watercolour Drawings by Reginald Jones". Doré Gallery, London, 1905.

- “Quayside Towns and English Landscapes”. Walker’s Galleries, London, 1913.
- “An exhibition of Water-colour Drawings, Oils and Pastels, by Reginald Jones, R.B.A”. Walker’s Galleries, London, 1915.

GROUP EXHIBITIONS

He exhibited “Silver Birch” at the Royal Academy in 1906 and “The Gipsy Encampment” in 1907. Additionally, “A Forest Stream” was exhibited at Institute of Painters in Oil Colours in 1884.

Unknown (Cottage and tree)

1883

165 x 240 mm

Watercolour on paper, 150 g/m²

JAMES POLLARD (1792-1867)

James Pollard was born in Baynes Spa Fields, later renamed Exmouth Street, in Islington, London, son of Robert Pollard the Elder. He went on to work for his father's firm as a draftsman and engraver. While working for his father he was commissioned by a print seller named Edward Orm to paint an inn's signboard, which would depict a mail-coach with horses and passengers. This commission launched the artist's career, for the sign post was seen by many prospective patrons. He was noted for his mail coach, fox hunting and equine scenes. Between 1821 and 1839 he exhibited at the Royal Academy and at the British Institution in 1824 and 1844. During his career he also worked with John Frederick Herring Snr on several horse racing paintings. Pollard painted the spectators and backgrounds whilst Herring painted the horses.

Many of Pollard's compositions were published as aquatints.

Today, his works are in the collections of the Art Institute of Chicago, the National Gallery of Art in Washington, D.C., the Tate Gallery in London, the Denver Art Museum, the Science Museum in London the Yale Center for British Art and the British Museum in London, amongst others.

The Mail Coach In A Drift Of Snow

1825

520 x 398 mm

Lithography on paper, watercolour hand-painted, 200 g/m²

GEORGE JAMES ROWE (1804-1883)

George James Rowe was a distinguished landscape artist who specialised in topographical, often moonlit scenes of Suffolk and London. His style fits with the British romantic landscape tradition and demonstrates influence from J.M.W Turner, John Constable and Thomas Gainsborough.

Rowe was born at Weeley Camp in Essex in 1804, the only son of George Rowe an army surgeon; in 1815 following a tour of duty in Ireland he opened a practice in Woodbridge, Suffolk, on the same street where Thomas Churchyard, would move to in 1825. George James Rowe and Churchyard became lifelong friends. Churchyard was also an aspiring artist. Both exhibited with the Norwich Society of British Artists. Early success inspired a move to London in 1832, sharing a studio but they soon returned to Suffolk having been deterred by both the competition and the costs. Rowe returned to London in 1844 and established himself in Fitzroy Square where he remained for the next forty years. He taught at the London School of Art and exhibited at the Royal Academy between 1830 and 1865.

Rowe's sister Anne Catherine Rowe emigrated to the United States of America in 1848 and became a friend of the Putnam family and donated many of Rowe's works to their collection hence much of Rowe's work has been hidden in the vaults of the Putnam Museum of History and Natural Science in Davenport, Iowa. The Putnam Museum has since dispersed its Rowe collection with many works having ended up in private hands and so it remains challenging to properly assess the extent of Rowe's work.

Today his works hang in the National Portrait Gallery London and in private collections..

Burgh Hall

1848 *ca.*

200 x 144 mm

Watercolour on paper, 120 g/m²

Shoreline

1848 *ca.*

200 x 145 mm

Watercolour on paper, 240g/m²

Global & Local Art Markets Consultants

Glocal Art Markets Consultants Ltd
Unit 24, 7 Fountayne Rd.
N15 4QL, London, United Kingdom
info@glocalartmarkets.com

© Glocal Art Markets 2021 | Registered Company Number 11777373 | www.glocalartmarkets.com
Design by Fabiola Wong

